

MACHINING OF REINFORCED ALUMINIUM AND MAGNESIUM

K. Weinert, D. Biermann and M. Liedschulte

Institut für Spanende Fertigung, University of Dortmund, 44221 Dortmund, Germany

SUMMARY: Several aluminium and magnesium alloys reinforced with different particles and short fibres have been machined for the investigations. The main problem for the machining of metal matrix composites (MMC) is tool wear, which is caused by the hard and abrasive reinforcements. Therefore it is necessary to find suitable cutting tools for the MMC and the different machining operations. In addition it is required to investigate the cutting conditions considering tool wear, surface quality, accuracy and surface integrity. In this paper the results of investigations concerning turning, milling and drilling of different MMC are presented.

KEYWORDS: metal matrix composites, turning, drilling, milling, wear mechanism, suitable cutting tool materials, diamond coated tools, subsurface zone

IMPORTANT MECHANISMS FOR THE MACHINING OF MMC

The main problem encountered in the conventional machining of MMC is tool wear, which is caused by the hard and abrasive reinforcements. A detailed analysis of the tribological system is necessary to understand the wear mechanism. Figure 1 shows a schematic representation of the elements and parameters of the cutting process. The reason for the extensive tool wear when machining MMC is the direct contact between the particles or fibres and the cutting edge. The dominant wear mechanism is abrasion which is generated by impacts at the cutting edge and relative sliding motion to the rake and clearance face of the cutting tool. These interactions lead to high mechanical and thermal loads. Important are the high dynamic stresses by the direct contact with the reinforcements.

For example: When turning particle reinforced aluminium with a useful reinforcement (volume fraction: 20 vol. %; grain size of the particles: 10 μm) and the listed parameters (cutting speed $v_c = 500$ m/min; feed rate $f = 0.1$ mm/rev; depth of cut $a_p = 1$ mm) about 20 million particles per second are separated with the chip. For the relation of the feed rate 0.1mm per revolution and the grain size about 10 μm it can be assumed, that nearly 2 million particles per second have direct contact with the cutting edge. This calculation shows clearly the high abrasive wear attack particularly at the cutting edge in form of microimpacts. Furthermore the direct sliding contact between reinforcement and rake face as well as clearance face abrade the cutting tool very intensive. Because of the high hardness of the reinforcements it can be similar to a grinding process if cutting tools with an insufficient hardness are used.

Fig. 1: Mechanical and thermal loads when machining MMC

Concerning the cutting tool materials it is important to consider their microstructural composition. Most of the cutting tool materials which are in common use consist of composite materials. For example: Cemented carbide consists of carbides as hard phase and a Co binder phase. Due to this, decisive factors are the properties of the reinforcement, particularly hardness, dimension and volume fraction but also hardness and grain size of the cutting tool material.

Very important for the comprehension of the cutting process concerning the tool wear are the abrasive wear mechanism: Microploughing, microfatigue, microcutting and microcracking [1]. Depending on the ratio of the properties between the reinforcements and the cutting tool materials the different abrasive wear mechanism are dominant:

Microploughing

Microploughing occurs when hard abrasives interact on the surface of a material which causes high plastic deformations. Several contacts of hard abrasives with microploughing lead to microfatigue. In general this mechanism is not dominant concerning the tool wear when machining MMC because the cutting tool materials have a high hardness and therefore a high resistance against plastic deformation. Nevertheless the high stress produced by the microcontacts between the reinforcement and the cutting tool can cause plastic deformation but the intensity concerning the tool wear is relative low.

Microcutting

The reinforcement removes material from the cutting tool in form of microchips. This mechanism is dominant if the reinforcement is harder than the cutting tool material and the dimension of the reinforcement is higher than the grain size of the hard phases of the cutting tool material.

Microcracking and Fatigue

The wear is produced by high dynamic loads which generates cracks into the cutting tool. These mechanism occur if the hardness and/or the grain size of the cutting tool material is higher compared with the properties of the reinforcements.

Comprehensive tests for the machining of aluminium matrix composites have shown that the suitability of the cutting tool materials mainly depends on the hardness of the reinforcements. But also the relation between the size of the reinforcements and the grain size of the cutting tool materials is important because these factors influence the dominant abrasive wear mechanism [2, 3, 4].

COMPARISON OF THE TOOL WEAR FOR THE MACHINING OF REINFORCED ALUMINIUM ALLOYS AND MAGNESIUM ALLOYS

In order to compare the influence of the matrix material on the machining process some magnesium matrix composites have been investigated. For example the results for milling of two different magnesium matrix composites with a short fibre reinforcement are summarized in Fig. 2. The shape of the cutting edge is described in the table tool geometry in which the main angles (α/α' : normal clearance/side clearance; γ/γ' : normal rake/side rake; κ/κ' : cutting edge angle/minor cutting edge angle) are quantified. The first point is the lower wear rate of polycrystalline diamond (PCD-MG) compared with cemented carbide (CC-MG). This result corresponds to the investigations for the machining of aluminium matrix composites [2]. Another point is the low difference of the wear rate between the different magnesium matrices (AZ 91, QE 22).

The scanning electron microscope (SEM) photographs show the worn cutting edges. The topography of the worn cutting edges are in accordance with the analyzed cutting tools used for the machining of short fibre reinforced aluminium alloys, so that the main wear mechanism can be transferred. Also the results for the machining of particle reinforced materials concerning the tool wear and the tribological mechanism are corresponding for aluminium and magnesium.

When machining δ -Al₂O₃-short fibre reinforced aluminium or magnesium the dominant abrasive wear mechanism is microcracking and fatigue. Because of the low hardness of δ -Al₂O₃-short fibres of approx. 800 HV it is not possible that the short fibre abrade the cemented carbide (approx. 1600 HV) or PCD (approx. 5000 HV) by microcutting. The hard phases of the cutting tools are abraded due to microcracking and fatigue at the cutting edge. The hard phases which are separated can also wear the cutting tool because they slide over the rake and clearance face due to the relative motion to the workpiece and the chips. Hereby the hard phases of cemented carbide (WC) effect like a polishing compound because of their small grain size of approx. 1.5-2 μ m and produce a very smooth topography of the worn surface. In the case of PCD the larger diamond grains (approx. 10 μ m) which are separated as a result of the wear attack by the reinforcements lead to very high local stresses at the cutting edge and can produce a wear out of the PCD insert by a self furrowing effect.

Fig. 3 shows a comparison between the tool wear when milling δ -Al₂O₃-short fibre reinforced magnesium alloys and an aluminium alloy with PCD. The difference between the values of the flank wear are relative low. This corresponds with the fact that also the differences between the strength of the matrix alloys is relative low (AlSi12CuMgNi: R_m = 295 MPa QE 22: R_m = 250 MPa, AZ 91: R_m = 220 MPa) [5, 6].

Fig. 2: Tool wear when milling reinforced magnesium with cemented carbide and PCD

Fig. 3: Tool wear when milling magnesium and aluminium with PCD

As an example for drilling SEM photographs of the tool wear of a cemented carbide drill when machining particle reinforced magnesium are depicted in Fig. 4. The different magnifications present a very regular flank wear. The photograph with the highest magnification (photograph in the middle of the figure) shows the topography of the worn surface which is characterized by grooves. These grooves are mainly parallel orientated to the cutting direction. This is the typical appearance of the wear topography when machining MMC with very hard reinforcements like SiC or B₄C particles. Because the hardness of cemented carbide is lower than the hardness of SiC and B₄C particles, these particles abrade the cemented carbide cutting tool by microcutting which is indicated by the grooves at the worn clearance face. This mechanism leads to a very extensive tool wear. Possibilities to reduce the tool wear are the use of harder cutting tool materials, for example PCD or diamond coatings, or the application of coarse grained cemented carbide [3].

Fig. 4: SEM photographs of the tool wear when drilling particle reinforced magnesium with cemented carbide drill

THE USE OF DIAMOND COATED CEMENTED CARBIDE

Due to the high cost of tools when using PCD, particularly of tools with a complex geometry, such as drills or thread drills, efforts must be made to find suitable coatings in this area. Very important demands are high hardness of the coating and a sufficient bonding between the substrate and the coating to achieve a high resistance against the abrasive wear attack. Former investigations have shown that TiAlN coating on cemented carbide is suitable for turning and drilling of δ -Al₂O₃-short fibre reinforced aluminium. When machining SiC or B₄C reinforced aluminium this coating is early abraded. Because of the very high hardness of SiC or B₄C particles the abrasive wear attack is too strong for this coating. Therefore the coating cannot protect the cutting tool so that there is nearly no advantage reachable compared with the uncoated cemented carbide tool [2, 7].

Diamond coatings are in principle suitable for turning of MMC because of their high hardness. However former investigations about the use of diamond coated cemented carbide tools have resulted that the wear protection is not very efficient. Because of the limited bonding between the coating and the cemented carbide substrate the coating breaks off due to the wear attack of the reinforcements [2].

For the development of suitable diamond coated tools the choice of the substrate material and its preparation is very important to achieve good nucleation of diamond and sufficient bonding between the coating and the substrate. A suitable approach to the problem of sufficient nucleation and adhesion of the diamond film is to use Si₃N₄ ceramic as substrates. In addition Si₃N₄ substrates have a good compatibility with thin diamond films because the deviation of the thermal expansion coefficient is relative low [8]. Therefore some good results have been achieved for the use of diamond coated Si₃N₄ cutting tools for the machining of reinforced aluminium [2]. However, because of lower toughness and higher cost of ceramic compared with cemented carbide particularly for cutting tools with a complex geometry, such as drills or thread drills, diamond coated ceramics are not a fundamental solution.

The use of cemented carbide as substrate is preferred because of the good combination of toughness, wear resistance and resistance to plastic deformation and furthermore the good flexibility to produce tools with a high variety of their shape. However, the binder phase of cemented carbide mainly consists of Co. Co is a good solvent for carbon and a good carbon carrier, it inhibits adhesion of diamond to the carbide substrate and also intensifies the formation of non-diamond material including soot [8]. Therefore an important prerequisite to achieve a suitable diamond coating is to remove the Co binder phase from the surface and the subsurface zone of the cemented carbide substrate. The research in this field leads to a further development of improved diamond coated cemented carbide tools.

Fig. 5 shows SEM photographs of a diamond coated cemented carbide insert. It can be seen that the coating has a very regular grain size and a relative smooth surface topography. The thickness of the coating amounts 10 - 12 μ m.

Fig. 5: SEM photographs of a diamond coated insert

Detailed analysis of the tool wear with SEM showed that for the machining of $\delta\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ short fibre reinforced aluminium the diamond coating is in a good condition after a cutting time of $t_c = 7.5$ min (Fig. 7). Only a slight wear in form of abraded diamond grains in the area of the cutting edge can be detected. When turning SiC-particle reinforced aluminium the tool wear is insignificant higher and the diamond coating is removed in places at the cutting edge. But nevertheless the remained coating is sufficient to protect the substrate. Also the wear rates for the diamond coating are in the range of the flank wear when machining with PCD.

The results concerning the tool wear for the use of the diamond coated cemented carbide are depicted in Fig. 6. The diagrams show the development of the flank wear when turning $\delta\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ short fibre (left side) and SiC-particle reinforced aluminium (right side). As reference the flank wear of uncoated cemented carbide tools is marked. In both cases the diamond coating leads to a considerable reduction of the tool wear. The high potential of the diamond coating can be estimated because of the low gradient of flank wear graphs.

Fig. 6: Tool wear when turning short fibre and particle reinforced aluminium with diamond coated cutting tools.

Fig. 7: SEM photographs of the tool wear of diamond coated inserts when turning short fibre reinforced aluminium.

SURFACE TOPOGRAPHY AND SUBSURFACE ZONE

Besides the tool wear another important factor is the surface integrity of MMC. Damage of the reinforcements, caused by the machining process, can lead to a decrease in the properties of the components. The cutting and deformation mechanism affects the surface quality in a multitude of ways. Examples are damages in the form of microcracks, pores, microstructural transformation, plastic deformation, residual stresses and changes in the hardness.

In order to analyze the influence of composite materials on the subsurface zone for turning, milling and drilling, SEM and optical microscope analysis of the machined surfaces and of special cross sections were carried out.

Fig. 8 shows SEM photographs of the surface topography and a cross section of the subsurface zone. PCD was used at a cutting speed of $v_c = 500$ m/min, a feed rate of $f_t = 0.05$ mm per tooth and a depth of cut which amounts to $a_p = 0.5$ mm. The surface exhibits a large number of pores, which primarily develop where individual particles or groups of particles are to be found in the boundary layer of the surface. Particle fragments can be clearly recognized in the area of the pore. The dimension of the fine grooves in the surface corresponds to the dimensions of the particles. Therefore the grooves are attributable to particles torn out in this area. Comparable results could be determined for the machining of short fibre reinforced materials.

Fig. 8: Surface topography and subsurface zone of a milled reinforced aluminium alloy.

The photograph of the cross section show the condition of the subsurface zone. The particles in the subsurface zone are subjected to enormous stress by the machining process. Particles which lie up to approximately 20 μm below to the surface are fractured as a result of plastic deformations.

In general it can be summarized that the surfaces of the machined MMC are characterized by pores and grooves attributable to fibres or particles turn out. Damages of the reinforcements, in form of fractures, in the subsurface zone can be caused by the cutting process. The fibre and/or particle fractures are found in a relatively small area of approx. 10 - 30 μm . The damages of the reinforcements increase due to higher specific cutting loads which are caused by the tool wear or the cutting parameters. An important point for milling operations is the ratio between the length of the minor edge chamfer and the feed rate. This influences the number of load cycles because of the contacts between the cutting tool and a defined surface section and therefore it also controls the level of the reinforcement damages.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to thank the DFG (Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft) for supporting these investigations.

REFERENCES

1. Zum Gahr, K.-H., "Microstructure and Wear of Materials", Tribology Series 10, Elsevier Amsterdam-Oxford 1987.
2. Biermann, D. "Untersuchungen zum Drehen von Aluminiummatrix-Verbundwerkstoffen", Fortschrittberichte, Reihe 2, Nr. 338, VDI Verlag Düsseldorf 1995.
3. Weinert, K., "A Consideration of Tool wear Mechanism when Machining Metal Matrix Composites (MMC)", Annals of the CIRP, Vol. 42, No. 1, 1993, pp.95-98.
4. Brun, M.K. and Lee, M., "Wear characteristics of Various Hard Materials for Machining SiC Reinforced Aluminium Alloy", The ASME Int. Conf. on Wear of Materials, Vancouver Canada 14.4.-18.4.1988, pp. 539-544.
5. Kainer, K.U., "Herstellung und Eigenschaften von faserverstärkten Magnesium-verbundwerkstoffen", in Metallische Verbundwerkstoffe, Eds.: Kainer, K.U., DGM Informationsgesellschaft Verlag, 1994, pp.219-244.
6. Henning, W. and Neite, G., "Herstellung, Eigenschaften und Anwendung von kurzfaserverstärkten Aluminiumlegierungen", in Metallische Verbundwerkstoffe, Eds.: Kainer, K.U., DGM Informationsgesellschaft Verlag, 1994, pp. 169-191.
7. Weinert, K., Biermann, D. and Meister, D., "Machining of Metal Matrix Composites - Tool Wear and Surface Integrity", Proc. ICCM-10, British Columbia, Canada, Aug. 14-18, 1995, Vol III, Eds.: Pousartip, A., Street, K.N., pp. 589-596.
8. Hintermann, H.E. and Chattopadhyay, A.K., "Low Pressure Synthesis of Diamond Coatings", Annals of the CIRP, Vol. 42, No. 2, 1993, pp. 769-783.